

Study of Tajik-Uzbek toponyms in the history of linguistics

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tilshunoslik tarixida toponimlar, xususan, tojikcha-o'zbekcha toponimlarning tadqiqi masalasi haqida fikrlar bayon etilgan.

Аннотация. В данной статье изложены взгляды на вопрос исследования топонимов в истории языкознания, в частности, таджикско-узбекских топонимов.

Annotation. This article presents views on the issue of toponymic research in the history of linguistics, in particular, Tajik-Uzbek toponyms.

In order to clarify the toponyms in our language and their theoretical foundations, a number of philological and toponymic term dictionaries in Tajik and Uzbek languages, textbooks and manuals created by toponym scientists, as well as books dedicated to toponym research. The information expressed in plab dissertations, monographs and articles is noteworthy.

In philological dictionaries, in particular, in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", the term "toponym" is a borrowed word, entered the Uzbek literary language from the Greek language as a borrowed word, and today Uzbek in the language, it is noted that it means "a set of geographical names of a place, area

(population, river, lake and other names)", as well as "a branch of lexicology that studies geographical names".

In "Farhangi Zaboni Tajiki" the word "toponymy" is explained in the sense of "combination of names of countries or subjects", "one part of a country, one name of a country"¹.

In the "Annotated dictionary of toponyms of the Uzbek language" it is mentioned that the term "toponym" is composed of the Greek words "topos" and "onuma" and this term means the name of a place. places (republic, region, city, district, village, village, district, daha, neighborhood, guzar), water bodies (ocean, sea, river, lake, reservoir, stream, tributary, pond, pond, stream)), understanding the names of landforms (mountain, peak, rock, height, hill, ravine, cave, field, pasture, hill)", as well as "sometimes geographical names, land-water names is described in the content.

In "Farhangi istilahoti zabonshinos" the term "toponym" is used in the Tajik literary language, especially in the field of toponymy, "the name of the place is natural, geographical, or at least human-made, on the planet, or in different regions (city, village, continent, land)." , including hydronym, oikonim, oronim, speleonim, horonim, urbanonim, insulonim, necronym" is recorded as a linguistic concept.

In this dictionary, the full details of the term "toponymy" are described along with the term "toponym". According to the information in the dictionary, "toponymy" (from Greek τόπος - place, space and onyma - name) is a part of onomastics, which describes the history, appearance, development, meaning, content and location of a name (toponym). meomuzad. Other branches of "toponymy" are hydronymics (the science of natural and man-made objects), cosmonymics (the science of the sky),

¹ Фарҳанги тафсирии забони тоҷикӣ. Ҷ.2. – Душанбе, 2008.305-б.

oikonimics (the science of local population), oronimics (the science of the relief of the earth).)" is mentioned to be divided into groups.

It should be said that there are different views on the definition and concept of toponymy. According to toponymist A.V. Superanskaya, "toponymics is a synthesis of linguistics, geography, and history," according to V.A. Zhuchkevich, toponymics is "an auxiliary science that studies geographic names." Superanskaya's point of view is closer to the truth, in our opinion. Since toponymy is a science that uses linguistic, geographical and historical analysis methods, toponyms are a part of linguistics because geographical names are a part of language and obey linguistic patterns. But they cannot be studied without knowing the culture and life of the people, that is, ethnography plays a big role in studying names.

Toponyms are geographical names that reflect the geographical laws and concepts of a specific area. In toponymy, the historical component is mandatory, but it is not only the history of countries and peoples, but also the history of languages. No historical event is directly reflected in the language. Its traces can only be indirectly identified in individual words.

From the point of view of linguistics, toponymy is not only a valuable resource for studying the history of language, but also important for the fields of etymology, dialectology, historical lexicology, and linguistic geography. Because some toponyms, in particular, hydronyms, archaisms and dialectisms have been preserved.

The first information about the toponym in the history of Turkic languages can be found in Abu Rayhan Beruni's works such as "India", "Qanuni Masudi", "Saydana". Abu Rayhan Beruni mentioned more than 400 geographical names in his work "Saydana" and more than 600 in his work "Qanuni Masudi".

Mahmud Kashgari's work "Devoni lugotit turk" is also of great importance in the study of place names. In addition to about a hundred names on the world card

attached to the work, 82 names of villages and cities, 68 names of countries, regions, regions, 25 names of seas, lakes, rivers, and streams are listed in the context. Geographical terms such as ort, sirt, yor, kair, dovan, yozi, dast, typical for the relief and natural conditions of our country, were first mentioned in the work "Devoni Lugotit Turk". The pronunciation of the word "jar" in the form of "yor", "yar" means that places like Yorboshi, Yortepa, Yorqtoy, Yorqin, Yorkhishloq, Yorgorgon, Akyor, Kuyganyor, Kokyor, Yortagi, Yorkocha were born. first emphasized in the work.

In addition, in Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's "Baburnoma" Marginon - Margilan, Uzgand - Uzgan, Qubo - Kuva, Khoqan - Koqan, Rushdon - Rishton, Sayhun - Khojand suyi or Sir suyi - Toponyms denoting geographical names such as Sirdarya were used.

It should be noted that the following terms related to toponymy are used in the Tajik language: anthroponym, toponymic base, toponymic word, toponymic area, toponymic region, toponymic system, toponymic study, toponymic substrate, toponymization, memory toponymy, statement of toponymy.

The services of R.Kh. Dodikhudoyev, Sh.Haydarov, J.Alimi, O.Gafurov, D.Homidov, A.Abdunabiyev in studying and researching the theoretical aspects of toponymy as Tajik scientists of toponymy are incomparable.

During the last ten years, it is possible to observe the practice of focusing on formative analysis and their structural analysis in many regional studies. This practice is directly related to N. Ofaridayev's "Economy of the Badakhshan Mountainous Autonomous Region", O. Mahmadjonov's "Toponymy and microtoponymy of the northern part of the Hisar Valley", M. Ayubovan's "Anthroponymy of Tajiks of Shahrituz and Qubodiyon Districts", D. Hamidov's "Toponymy of Keshrud Valley", N. Khojayevarir "Development dynamics of geographical images of Central Asia in

ancient and early medieval Iranian traditions", S. Sheraliyevanir "Development of Khatlon region hydronymy", J. Alimi "Kolob region toponymy", S.M. Imamzoda "Studies on nomenclature and naming", "Toponymy of the Rasht Valley of Tajikistan" by Sh. Ismailov, "Lexical-semantic research and pronunciation of the microtoponymy of the Yaghnob Valley" by B. Torayev and "Researches of the microtoponymy of the Yaghnob Valley" appears in the

E.M. Mirzayev is recognized as the founder of modern geotonymic research. He developed methods of obtaining geographical classification information from folk geographic terms. He justified the fact that toponyms are a unique tool that provides real information about the geographical environment.

In Y.M. Pospelov's studies, importance is attached to the mathematical and cartographic aspects of toponymy, folk terminology, methods of using toponyms in the process of teaching geography.

Let's look at the history of some toponyms in our country:

"Koli Shagolon", horonym "Tumani Gajdumak", hydronym "Daryoi Gardoni Javzo", common name "Dehayi Lattaband" and so on.

The toponymic material used by the writers and poets of the people is of great importance for toponymy experts and linguists. Here, with a special sense of responsibility, he gives detailed information about the date of construction, the initiators of construction, the location of denotations and other aspects. All this helped the reader to get detailed information about the history of the cities and villages where his ancestors lived.

In conclusion, it should be said that geographical names are a historical part of the people, represent different periods of the development of the language and culture of the society, and their research is considered the main object of study of linguistics. In this regard, artistic-aesthetic intended by choosing and using oikonym, comonym,

astionim, urbanonym, godonym, agoronym, ekklesionim, oronym, hydronym, zootonym, anthroponym, ethnotonym, phytophoric and other types of toponyms used in the works of writers, g It is clear that it states the spiritual goals.

List of used literature:

1. Aynī S. Dokhunda. - Dushanbe: Irfon, 1984. - p. 347.
2. Aynī S. It's a memory. Volume 6. Part 1–2. - Dushanbe: "Tajikistan State Publishing House", 1962. - p. 288.
3. Farhangi tafsirii zaboni Tajik.J.2. - Dushanbe, 2008. p. 305.
4. Mohammad Narshahi. History of Bukhara. - Tashkent: Science, 1966. - 108 p.
5. Nafasov T. Explanatory dictionary of toponyms of Uzbekistan (southern regions of Uzbekistan). - Tashkent: "Teacher", 1988. B- 288.